

A STUDY ON CUSTOMERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ONLINE RESERVATION IN MADURAI CITY

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Abstract:

An online reservation system or central reservation system (CRS) is a computerized system used to store and retrieve information and conduct transactions related to air travel, hotels, bus travel, rail travel, or any other activity. In general, reservation means an act of reserving or arranging to have something for use in advance. Originally designed and operated by airlines, CRSes were later extended for the use of travel agencies. Major CRS operations that book and sell tickets for multiple airlines are known as Global Distribution System (GDS). Airlines have divested most of their direct holdings to dedicated GDS companies who make their systems accessible to consumers through internet gateways. Modern GDSes typically allow users to book hotel rooms, rental cars, airline tickets as well as activities and tours. They also provide access to railway reservations and bus reservations in some markets, although these are not always integrated with the main system. There are a lot of booking sites using this option now. Nowadays, the internet is available to almost to everyone. So the online e-booking system has become a new trend. Many companies have its own e-booking facility. An individual with a positive attitude towards a product and service offering is more likely to make a purchase. This makes the study of consumer attitudes highly important for a marketer. An attitude may be defined as a feeling of favourableness or unfavourableness that an individual has towards an object (be it a person, thing or situation). It is a learned predisposition to exhibit and act based on evaluation, resulting in a feeling of like or dislike towards an object. In terms of consumer behaviour, consumer attitudes may be defined as "an inner feeling of favourableness or unfavourableness towards a product or service offering". Hence the study has made an attempt to analyse the "Customers Attitude towards Online Reservation in Madurai City".

Introduction:

The new era of information technology has brought multiple advantages to mankind. The world has seen a great technological boom in the last fifty years, with innovations in every field making it possible for human life to be more easier and comfortable. Tickets are documents that confirm the purchase and guarantee a seat on a chosen journey, hotel or for a show. Tickets are required as proof to get a boarding pass which is essential. Traditional tickets of earlier days were made of paper and were to be collected from the travel agencies or office for purchasing. Along with globalization and the development of the aviation industry, the process of ticket purchasing has also changed. Since the rapid growth and use of the internet since the 2000s, reservation has been possible online. In particular, the internet has allowed us to search for any reservations or purchases right from our own place and find the best offers just at the click of a button. More and more people all over the world prefer to buy products through different websites. Apart from consumer goods, sales and e-tailing, the online travelling sector has boomed in recent years and the number of users booking their tickets on the Web has been steadily growing. Decreasing number of people are now using the traditional paper ticket while almost all industries offer the possibility of online ticket reservation, commonly known as e-ticket. We now live in an era where practically everything is inextricable from the internet, including business. It's now crucial that every business, no matter the sector, has a recognisable web presence, because Google has replaced the phone book. Not only does internet technology help tour and activity operators get found online, it also helps them convert visits into money through online booking or reservation systems. Since the rise of online travel in the mid-1990s, it seems that there are an endless number of ways to fix one's travel itinerary. Due to the emergence of the online reservation system, selections are made available online making it easy to book nearly any sort of trip at any time. This turns into plenty of bookings. It has been projected that by the year 2012, there will be 98.3 million bookings on the Internet, which translates into major profits for online travel companies. So, the recent scenario has changed the traditional booking systems into the newest electronic reservation system. .

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To analyse the customer attitude towards online reservation.
- ✓ To study the awareness of Online reservation of consumers in Madurai

Statement of the Problem: Transport is an important part of the Indian economy. Since the economic liberalisation of the 1990s, infrastructure development has progressed rapidly and today there are a variety of

modes of transport. Public transport remains the primary mode of transport for most of the population, and India's public transport systems are among the most heavily used in the world. Despite ongoing improvements in the sector, several aspects of the transport sector are still riddled with problems due to outdated infrastructure. The demand for transport infrastructure and services has been rising year by year with the current infrastructure being unable to meet these growing demands. It is needless to affirm that, online reservation is a new way of thinking about how transport sectors can target increasing number of customers with a beneficial change. Customers meet many problems during ticket reservation. Problems arise in booking tickets through counters, spending time by waiting in queues, reservation form filling, carrying cash for lump booking, risk of confirmation and so on. Now-a-days online reservation has become a highly sought after alternative for booking tickets. Therefore, transport sectors spend a lot of time and money in developing online reservation systems to satisfy customers. Hence this study has made an attempt to know, "Customer attitude towards online reservation in Madurai city"

Chi – Square Test:

Relationship Between Educational Qualification of the Respondents and the Medium Through Which They Book Tickets Online:

H₀ = There is no relationship between educational qualification of the respondents and the medium through which they book tickets online.

Table 1

Particulars	Myself	Travel Agents	With the Help of Knowledge Person	Browsing Centres	Others	Total
Illiterate	0	0	0	0	0	0
Schooling	0	0	2	0	0	2
Under graduate	1	2	1	3	0	7
Post graduate	0	3	5	2	3	13
Professional	12	7	15	5	8	47
Others	1	2	11	11	6	31
Total	14	14	34	21	17	100

Source: Primary data

Degree of Freedom	Calculated Value	Level of Significance	Table Value
20	25.64	5%	31.4

Table 1 shows that the value of χ^2 for degree of freedom 20 at 5% level of significance is 31.4. The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, it is inferred that there is no significant relationship between educational qualification of the respondents and the medium through which they book tickets online.

Relationship Between the Gender and the Purpose for Which They Book Online:

H₀= There is no relationship between the gender and the purpose for which they book online.

Table 2

Particulars	Leisure Travel	Business/ Office Trip	Routine Travel	Medical Treatment	Ceremonies	Research and Studies	Others	Total
Male	11	13	10	3	3	4	7	51
Female	6	23	7	3	8	1	1	49
Total	17	36	17	6	11	5	8	100

Source: Primary data

Degree of Freedom	Calculated Value	Level of Significance	Table Value
6	13.26	5%	12.6

Source: Primary data

Table 2 shows that the value of χ^2 for degree of freedom 6 at 5% level of significance is 12.6. The calculated value of χ^2 is greater than the table value. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is inferred that there is significant relationship between the gender and the purpose for which they book online.

Relationship Between the Gender and the Purpose for Which They:

H₀= There is no relationship between the gender and the purpose for which they book online.

Table 3

Particulars	Leisure Travel	Business/ Office Trip	Routine Travel	Medical Treatment	Ceremonies	Research and Studies	Others	Total
Male	11	13	10	3	3	4	7	51
Female	6	23	7	3	8	1	1	49
Total	17	36	17	6	11	5	8	100

Source: Primary data

Degree of Freedom	Calculated Value	Level of Significance	Table Value
6	13.26	5%	12.6

Source: Primary data

Table 3 shows that the value of χ^2 for degree of freedom 6 at 5% level of significance is 12.6. The calculated value of χ^2 is greater than the table value. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is inferred that there is significant relationship between the gender and the purpose for which they book online.

Garret Ranking Technique:

Garret ranking technique is applied to rank the sources of awareness of the respondents.

Table 4: Ranking of the Sources of Awareness

Sources of Awareness	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Garret score	Average score	Rank
Magazines	17	31	17	14	8	6	7	5743	820.43	I
Travel agents	16	10	8	32	16	14	4	5210	744.28	II
Search engines/ email notification	24	3	10	15	10	23	15	4944	706.28	IV
News paper	18	10	13	13	16	14	16	4955	707.86	III
Friends/Colleagues	12	16	15	7	18	10	22	4759	679.86	VI
Media	12	12	18	8	15	19	16	4782	683.14	V
Others	1	15	20	11	20	14	19	4468	638.28	VII

Source : Primary Data

Table 4 shows that magazines ranks first, travel agents ranks second, third rank was given for newspapers by the respondents, fourth rank to search engines/email notifications, fifth rank to media, sixth rank to friends/colleagues and the last rank to other sources

Table 5: Websites for Booking Train Tickets Online

Websites	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Garret Score	Average Score	Rank
irctc.com	10	8	7	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	2089	189.90	I
yatra.com	1	8	2	-	-	6	2	-	-	-	-	1179	107.18	VI
redbus.com	12	-	-	3	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	1383	125.73	II
cleartrip.com	5	-	-	-	-	3	7	-	-	-	-	880	80	IX
indianrail.gov.in	-	-	9	-	5	3	6	-	-	-	-	1280	116.36	IV
newindianexpress.com	3	4	3	7	1	-	2	-	-	-	-	1290	117.27	III
zoomtra.com	2	5	-	3	4	5	2	-	-	-	-	1263	114.82	V
goibibo.com	2	1	3	-	6	6	-	-	-	-	-	1063	96.64	VIII
ixigo.com	-	2	-	2	5	1	-	-	-	-	-	587	53.36	X
bookmytrain.com	-	2	6	2	2	1	6	-	-	-	-	1082	98.36	VII
Others	-	-	3	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	403	36.64	XI

Source : Primary Data

The table 5 shows that irctc.com ranks first, redbus.com ranks second, newindianexpress.com ranks third, indianrail.gov.in ranks fourth, zoomtra.com ranks fifth, yatra.com ranks sixth, bookmytrain.com ranks seventh, goibibo.com ranks eighth, cleartrip.com ranks ninth, ixigo.com ranks tenth and the last rank to other websites.

Conclusion:

As a commercial medium, the web offers a number of advantages for all the customers and companies. From the customer point of view, using the web instead of a traditional approach called for tickets or go to a travel agency means way into a greater amount of information and also more flexibility in choosing, analysing and comparing the offers. Having more choices with just a click away helps customers find a better deal, in possibly least time. For the companies, the use of the Web means decrease costs for information processing, reduced costs to suppliers, the possibility of building stronger customer relationships with will customers interact directly with the web site, the possibility of creating user profiles to be used in marketing development and also an easy way of information partnership, involving the cooperation between different companies. Online Reservation System has its effectiveness in booking frequency, especially in keeping hotel contracting room and allotment updated in real-time manner. It helps the service providers in having them updated about the availability. In this study it is found that magazine is found to be the main source of awareness to the consumers. In the study the attitude of the consumers found highly very positive towards online ticket booking than their negative attitudes. The consumers have high level of satisfaction in online reservation because it is instant and since it has guide and help, it is found to be one of the major way for reservation than that of brick and portal model. The suggestions were given to the service providers to focus its attention mainly on delighting the customer and to fulfil the requirements and expectation. Thus, in this study the researchers had made an attempt

to find out the customers' suggestions about the online reservation system and also varied solution have been given to improve the customers' requirements, and service which in turn could earn goodwill among public.

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